

WAYS TO IMPLEMENT AND IMPROVE GREEN ENERGY PRINCIPLES IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *This article discusses the need for green energy projects in the country and the possible problems to implement them. Moreover, in the article the problems will be discussed and the possible ways to tackle with them will be suggested according to the case of Uzbekistan. Suggestions and discussed possible problems have been analyzed according to the statistics.*

Keywords: *green energy, infrastructure, foreign investment, oil production, decarbonization, renewable energy.*

Introduction

Over the past years increasing consumption of energy and severing climate change issues has made the transformation of energy system even more crucial. According to statistics of the IEA (International energy agency) in 2023, energy production and industry are responsible for nearly 40% of carbon emission. The case has drawn most countries to the implementation of alternative ways to substitute traditional energy sources, and prevent even more severe possible problems of environment. This has urged to develop new technologies, infrastructures and methods to process energy sources, and find new sources to use traditional ones wisely.

In the case of Uzbekistan, sectors of industry constitute almost 30-35% of GDP and dominates the most proportion of energy consumption. For this reason, it is becoming more and more important for the country to implement green energy principles to maintain constant development. Moreover, the implementation of green energy sources and the ways to accomplish this principle will enable the country to contribute global affairs to save the nature.

Main part

Before going deep into the analysis and the statistics of energy sources, we will discuss what the green energy and what kind of principles will be applied. According to the website definition of National grid in the UK, “Green energy is energy that can be produced using a method, and from a source, that causes no harm to the natural environment”. As mentioned in the definition, green energy sources do not harm the environment, which is the main concern of searching new alternative energy sources and making them popular among consumers. Environmental affairs have made it necessary to alter energy sources and the processing of them by which further severe issues related to it could be facilitated to some extent. Moreover, the past years have proven that alternative energy sources can be viable in several cases.

The renewable energy sector was also able to quickly adapt to the new market conditions that emerged as a result of the pandemic. This enabled the rapid commissioning of new renewable energy installations within the planned time frames in countries such as China, the United States, and Vietnam. Moreover, during the crisis period, many governments—including those of the United States, China, India, and the European Union—demonstrated an increased willingness to accelerate the deployment of renewable energy technologies. For all renewable energy

technologies, long-term targets and policy stability in this sector are of critical importance to ensure investor confidence and sustained development. At the same time, governments need to continuously adapt to changing market conditions in order to enhance competitiveness and improve the integration of renewable energy sources into the global energy system.

According to the reports of the UNDP (United Nations Development Project) in 2021, using energy sources, such as solar, tidal, wind and others, can reduce greenhouse gases by 70%. The conception of constant development means effective use of energy and decarbonization. This, in turn, means optimal industrial use of energy and ecologically friendly energy sources.

Fuel and energy sources of Uzbekistan is rich. Uzbekistan national company "Uzbekneftgaz" occupies 11th rank over the world according to its natural gas production. There are 194 hydrocarbon deposits in Uzbekistan, and 98 of them are gas and gas-condensate fields while the others oil-gas, oil-gas-condensate fields. In Uzbekistan 3.4 trillion cubic meters of oil is produced every year.

It should be emphasized that Uzbekistan had planned to implement 30 investment projects related to the fields of geological exploration, hydrocarbon extraction, and processing by 2030. For this reason, the issue of intensifying oil production remains really relevant in the case of Uzbekistan. Nowadays, in the country oil import dependency is high as its oil production potential has been declining while the scale of its consumption proceeds to rise. The country is planning to import about 2 million tons of oil every year from neighbour country Kazakhstan.

However, to receive and process such volume of oil production, the country should complete necessary oil transportation construction and oil refining infrastructures in the field. The shares of energy consumption is divided in several sectors. Major amount of energy consumption goes to industrial use. Their proportions are as follows:

1. Over 60 % of energy in the country is produced by thermal electric stations.
2. Natural gas constitutes 80% of energy production.
3. Industrial consumption of energy is nearly 45-50%.

However, in some industrial companies energy efficiency is low, and in some cases their loss of energy is about 20-25%. This loss can lead to increase of expenses and ecological issues. For this reason, transformation to green energy is crucial for several reasons and we will discuss the principles to implement this in industrial process.

One of them is the need to enhance renewable energy sources. Potential of solar energy is higher thanks to the duration of sunny days, approximately 300 days a year. According to the statistics of 2020 reported by Asian Development Bank, Uzbekistan can produce 50 billion W energy by solar power. Another principle is increasing energy efficiency. According to the research carried out by World Bank in 2022, increasing energy efficiency can reduce its consumption by 20-30%. Moreover, there is a need for introducing new technologies to the field. For example, smart grid and digital monitoring system that can enable to control energy consumption on time and constantly.

Finally, empowering political system to transform energy policy is one of vital steps to change the pattern. For example, in recent years several projects supporting renewable energy sources have been implemented in Uzbekistan. They include solar, wind stations that are being financed by international investment.

However, transformation to green energy can cause some problems. One of them is mentioned above. Green energy requires high investment that can be difficult to find. For example, according to the statistics of the IEA in 2023, majority of green energy projects have been halted due

to a lack of sufficient financial support. Moreover, this is a new phenomenon that is developing nowadays, so the need for technological knowledge and experience is vital. The lack of it is another potential problem lies behind the implementation. In addition, integration of renewable energy sources can be problematic.

To cope with these problems there are several ways to facilitate the situation. One of them is funding green energy projects with the cooperation of state and personal investment and encouraging this cooperation. This can tackle with the financial problems to some extent and enable to implement the project at least in limited scope. Moreover, another step can be stricter rules and standards to control energy efficiency. Developing and improving scientific research area in the field of energy to find more alternative ways to implement the project and find reliable sources to use and develop. This can require to integrate and adapt foreign research results and their methods to apply. This could widen the scope of the research area.

Conclusion

In conclusion, nowadays environmental and economic issues are demanding to adjust energy consumption to the needs and the demands. In the case of Uzbekistan, introducing green energy principles will require to maintain economic efficiency, energy security and ecological consideration. According to the analysis and discussion of the statistics, it is clear that Uzbekistan has enough natural resources that could be used wisely to maintain further use, and the introduction of new technologies and methods can sustain positive results in energy consumption.

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